

Emotional Intelligence and Anti- Social Behavior in Relation to Social Skills of the Juveniles in the City of Mati: A Regression Analysis

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Abstract:- This study determined the level of emotional intelligence, anti-social behavior, and social skills and which domains significantly influence the level of social skills among juveniles, in the City of Mati. The study used the non-experimental quantitative research design with descriptive-correlational technique, the researcher examines the relationship between three variables in a natural setting without manipulation. The respondents were 300 juveniles chosen using a stratified random sampling technique. The researcher employed a mixed method of face-to-face and online survey during the gathering of data. An adapted modified survey questionnaire was used in the gathering of data. Mean and regression analysis was used in analyzing and interpreting the data. Results in the study revealed a moderate level of emotional intelligence among juveniles in terms of self-awareness, self-motivation, and self-regulation. On the contrary, the level of anti-social behavior among juveniles is gauged in terms of aggression, vandalism, theft, anti-normative conduct, and drug-related which resulted to low. As to the level of social skills, the result further revealed a moderate level in terms of interpersonal behavior, self-related behavior, task-related behavior, and environment-related behavior. More so, a significant relationship existed between social skills and emotional intelligence while anti-social behavior and social skills showed no significance in the study. Nevertheless, the study revealed only that emotional intelligence best influences the level of social skills among juveniles in the City of Mati.

Keywords:- social skills, emotional intelligence, antisocial behavior, juvenile, regression, path analysis, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most predominant problems affecting children worldwide is student delinquency. It was reported that in 2011 as per record appearing in the Ministry of Education, there were a total of 111,484 students in Selangor, both in primary and secondary schools, who were involved in student delinquency, majority of them had record cases in truancy and crime, few had committed disciplinary problems, and others were into pornography and vandalism (Arum & Ford, 2012).

Similarly, the juvenile's emotional intelligence is often associated with aggression; adolescents with delinquent behavior also experience emotional troubles and issues. In his study, youngsters who possessed low emotional

intelligence were found to have been involved in delinquent behaviors like illegal substance use, vandalism, and violent activities, which caused danger in many aspects (Johnston, 2003).

Moreover, a deficiency in an individual's social skill level has been linked with various behavioral and attitude problems in children and adolescents, including delinquency (Van der Laan et al. 2009). Specifically, a person with low social skills has a higher risk of offending and criminal offense recidivism. Many children who have not acquired appropriate social skills develop psychological problems such as unsuccessful communication with peers, inappropriate educational performance, not participating in activities and isolation, rejection by peers, anxiety, depression, and anger in childhood and throughout life (Anastasi, 1990).

While it is true that educators have been searching for the most effective methods for promoting social competence in students with emotional and behavior disorders this time of the pandemic, conversely, the researcher identified significant gaps from the studies that showed literature studies in this area of emotional intelligence, anti-social behavior and social skills which may manifest problems among children that will result to a negative impact and on their behavior such as aggression and committing of offenses. Last year, 3% of the crime recorded in Mati City were juvenile crimes. Just recently, there were seven minors rescued in the Barangay Central after being spotted in the Belsonda area amid the curfew hours.

Upon learning these prevailing scenarios, the researcher finds urgency in conducting this study as this may contribute to the conceptualization of programs and interventions specific to the well-being of the juveniles, particularly in terms of social skills and emotional intelligence, which may help in reducing inappropriate behaviors, particularly those who are vulnerable in engaging to anti-social acts, children in conflict with the law and children at risk by exploring the level of emotional intelligence, anti-social behavior, and social skills, as well as the influence of emotional intelligence and anti-social behavior on the social skills of juveniles in the City of Mati.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized a standardized research questionnaire to answer the study's objectives. The first questionnaire deals with emotional intelligence, which contains self-awareness, Self-regulation, and Self-motivation (Goleman, 1995). The second questionnaire focuses on anti-social behavior; the researcher utilized the downloaded questionnaire of Dos Santos et al. (2019), represented by the following indicators: aggression, theft, vandalism, anti-normative conduct, and drug-related. And finally, in the third questionnaire, social skills include interpersonal behavior, self-related behavior, task-related behavior, and environment-related behavior (Zsolnai and Lasik, 2014).

The questionnaires were constructed to include only relevant items to the study. Each indicator for both variables contain numerous items to provide a clearer picture of the responses. The researcher presented the first draft of the questionnaire to the adviser for comments, and suggestions, after which the experts were requested to validate the said questionnaire. The validators suggested many corrections and recommendations, which the researcher compiled before the data gathering. Hence the last revision was made incorporating all the additional inputs in the instrument. The final copies were submitted to a panel of experts for refinement. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.38, which has a verbal description of very good. Additionally, the University Research Ethics Committee approved the said instrument regarding the requirements needed for confidentiality, respondent's rights, and other ethical issues.

In evaluating the level of emotional intelligence of the juveniles, the scale below was used.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very high	The measures of emotional intelligence are always manifested
3.40-4.19	High	The measure of emotional intelligence are often manifested
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The measures of emotional intelligence are sometimes manifested
1.80-2.59	Low	The measures of emotional intelligence are seldom manifested
1.00-1.79	Vey low	The measures of emotional intelligence are almost never manifested

In determining the level of anti-social behavior, this range of means and interpretation was used.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very high	The measures of emotional intelligence are always observed
3.40-4.19	High	The measure of emotional intelligence are often observed
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The measures of emotional intelligence are sometimes observed
1.80-2.59	Low	The measures of emotional intelligence are seldom observed
1.00-1.79	Vey low	The measures of emotional intelligence are almost never observed

Lastly, in determining the level of social skills of the juveniles, the scale below was used.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very high	The measures of social skills are always manifested
3.40-4.19	High	The measures of social skills are often manifested
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The measures of social skills are sometimes manifested
1.80-2.59	Low	The measures of social skills are seldom manifested
1.00-1.79	Vey low	The measures of social skills are almost never manifested

Furthermore, for a more comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, Mean was used to measure the level of emotional intelligence, anti-social behavior, and social skills of the juveniles in the City of Mati and Regression Analysis was used to measure the significant relationships and influence of emotional intelligence and anti-social behavior on the social skills of the juveniles.

III. RESULTS

A. Emotional Intelligence of Juveniles

The first objective of this study is to measure the level of emotional intelligence of juveniles as they evaluated themselves. Shown in Table 1 is the result from the tabulated data. It is measured in terms of self-awareness, self-regulation, and self-motivation. The level of emotional intelligence was sometimes manifested by the juveniles in the City of Mati. It reaches an overall mean of 2.84, which indicates moderate, and the overall standard deviation is 0.52. This shows that the respondents' response ranges from 2.82 to 2.89 which is all at a moderate level.

From this data, self-awareness has the highest mean score of 2.89 which means moderate. This only means that the juveniles sometimes manifested self-awareness with a standard deviation of 0.60.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-awareness	0.60	2.89	Moderate
Self-regulation	0.59	2.82	Moderate
Self-motivation	0.61	2.82	Moderate
Overall	0.52	2.84	Moderate

Table 1: Level of Emotional Intelligence of Juveniles

While on the contrary, self-regulation and self-motivation have the lowest mean score of both 2.82 and a standard deviation of 0.59 and 0.61 respectively, which also means moderate, that the juveniles sometimes manifested in the level of their emotional intelligence.

B. Anti-social Behavior

Another objective of this research study is to determine the level of anti-social behavior of juveniles. As shown in Table 2, the results of the tabulated data were gathered. The level of anti-social behavior of juveniles' is gauged in terms of aggression, vandalism, theft, anti-normative conduct, and

drug-related. The level of anti-social behavior has an overall mean of 2.07, which means low and expresses that the juveniles seldom committed the anti-social behavior while the overall standard deviation is 0.98.

This further justifies that the respondents' response ranges from 1.76 to 2.30, which falls from the descriptive level of low. Drawn from this data, aggression and anti-normative conduct have the highest mean score of 2.30, which means low, that the juveniles seldom committed the anti-social behavior and a standard deviation of 1.20 and 1.30 respectively.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Aggression	1.20	2.30	Low
Vandalism	1.20	2.12	Low
Theft	1.19	1.86	Low
Anti-normative conducts	1.13	2.30	Low
Drug-related	1.04	1.76	Low
Overall	0.98	2.07	Low

Table 2: Level of Antisocial Behavior of Juveniles

In addition, vandalism obtained the second highest mean score of 2.12 or low, which means that the juveniles seldom committed anti-social behavior and a standard deviation of 1.20. Subsequently; theft has the third-highest mean score of 1.86, which means that juveniles seldom committed the anti-social behavior and a standard deviation of 1; the lowest mean is drug-related with a mean score of 1.76 or low which means that the juveniles seldom committed the anti-social behavior and a standard deviation of 1.04.

C. Social Skills

The third objective of this study is to describe the level of social skills of juveniles. Table 3 shows the results of the tabulated data gathered with interpretation. The level of social skills of juveniles' is presented in terms of interpersonal behavior, self-related behavior, task-related behavior, and environment-related behavior. The level of social skills has an overall mean of moderate and signifies that the juveniles sometimes manifested the social skills while the overall standard deviation is 0.58.

The data revealed the highest mean, interpersonal behavior, which is moderate, best explains that juveniles sometimes manifested the social skills with a standard deviation of 0.68.

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Interpersonal behavior	0.68	2.88	Moderate
Self-related behavior	0.70	2.77	Moderate
Task-related behavior	0.70	2.72	Moderate
Environmental-related behavior	0.83	2.73	Moderate
Overall	0.58	2.77	Moderate

Table 3: Level of Social Skills of Juveniles

From the table above, the second-highest mean is self-related behavior with a rating of 2.77 standard deviations of 0.70 means that the juveniles sometimes manifested the social skills. Moreover, environment-related behavior has the third-highest mean of 2.70 with a standard deviation of 0.83 means that juveniles sometimes manifested social skills. On the other note, task-related behavior has the lowest mean of 2.72 with a standard deviation of 0.70 means

justifies that juveniles sometimes manifested the social skills.

D. Significance of the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Social Skills of Juveniles

The fourth objective of this study was to establish a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and the social skills of the juveniles. Figures of computation are presented in Table 4. The p-value signifies the strength of the relationship of the variables tested in the study.

Emotional Intelligence	Social Skills				Overall
	Interpersonal Behavior	Self-regulated Behavior	Task-related Behavior	Environmental-related Behavior	
Self-awareness	.576**	.534**	.428**	.398**	.604**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Self-regulation	.617**	.535**	.482**	.411**	.637**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Self-motivation	.648**	.562**	.569**	.387**	.673**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.709**	.628**	.570**	.460**	.737**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Social Skills of Juveniles

As revealed in the table, all the indicators of emotional intelligence when analyzed according to the indicators of social skills, the obtained f-ratio between the specified ranges was .737 with a p-value of .000, which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance rejected the null hypothesis. In other words, the null hypothesis which revealed no significant relationship on the level of emotional intelligence when analyzed according to the level of social skills of the juveniles in the City of Mati was rejected.

E. Significance of the Relationship between Antisocial Behavior and Social Skills

Revealed in Table 5 is the significant relationship between antisocial behavior and the social skills of juveniles. As shown in the result of this study, the overall rating of the f-ratio which was .073 with a p-value of .209, was greater than the 0.05 level of significance and failed to reject the null hypothesis. It only means that the researcher found no significance in the relationship between antisocial behavior and social skills of juveniles in the City of Mati.

Antisocial Behavior	Social Skills				Overall
	Interpersonal Behavior	Self-regulated Behavior	Task-related Behavior	Environmental-related Behavior	
Aggression	-.086	.021	.076	.059	.025
	.135	.712	.192	.309	.671
Vandalism	-.075	.008	.161**	.017	.035
	.198	.893	.005	.771	.549
Theft	-.094	.028	.179**	.132*	.081
	.104	.635	.002	.022	.159
Anti-normative Conducts	-.038	-.015	.120*	.101	.056
	.509	.795	.038	.081	.334
Drug-related	-.037	.062	.189**	.153**	.120*
	.529	.284	.001	.008	.038
Overall	-.079	.024	.169**	.106	.073
	.173	.684	.003	.066	.209

Table 5: Significance on the Relationship between Antisocial Behavior and Social Skills of Juveniles

On the other hand, it was revealed also the obtained f-ratio between task-related behavior and theft which was .179 with a p-value of .002 which was also lower than the 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The same goes with the statistical result between the drug-related and task-related behavior which had a result of .001, lower than the 0.05 level of significance which further claimed the null hypothesis was rejected, hence this shows a significant relationship.

F. Significance on the Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Antisocial Behavior on the Social Skills

Presented in Table 4 are the regression coefficients to test the significant influence of overall emotional intelligence, anti-social behavior on the social skills of the juveniles. The level of significance was tested at .005. Using regression analysis, the data achieved that the overall level of emotional intelligence significantly influences the social skills of juveniles since the influence of emotional intelligence on the social skills of the juveniles has a p-value of .000.

Social Skills				
(Variables)	<i>B</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Constant	.376		2.817	.005
Emotional Intelligence	.818	.736	18.865	.000
Antisocial Behavior	.036	.061	1.574	.117
R	.740			
R ²	.548			
ΔR ²	.544			
F	179.690			
P	.000 ^b			

Table 6: Significance on the Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Antisocial Behavior on the Social Skills of Juveniles

Furthermore, shown in Table 6 is the insignificant result of the relationship between levels of anti-social behavior and social skills. The result revealed that the t-values of anti-social behavior $t=1.574$. Among the two variables, only emotional intelligence has a significant influence on the social skills of the juveniles as manifested in the p-values, which are less than 0.05. Finally, the variable that best influences the social skills of the juveniles is emotional intelligence with an unstandardized coefficient beta value of 18.865

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Emotional Intelligence of the Juveniles

The juveniles sometimes manifested the level of emotional intelligence in the City of Mati, it reaches an overall mean of 2.84, which indicates moderate, and the general standard deviation is 0.52. This shows that the respondents' response ranges from 2.82 to 2.89, all at an intermediate level.

Although the result is moderate, deficiencies in emotional intelligence skills still affect people in any manner, especially students who are in and out of school. Moreover, it was also proved that high school students possessing deficiencies in the level of emotional intelligence show greater predictability toward violent and criminal tendencies (Liau et al., 2003).

The inability of an individual to understand emotion in oneself and others can be changed, and how people react to a different set of emotions would contribute to delinquency. As indicated, students who have higher levels of emotional intelligence were hypothesized to be linked with lower chances of internalizing disruptive behavior like as academic stress, depression, somatoform disorders, and constant anxiety, as well as lower levels of externalizing deviant behavior, such as violent acts and delinquency (Liau et al., 2003).

Moreover, a longitudinal study was conducted, which showed that delinquent students were found to lack self-control. A child's emotional being impacts their behavior; research further showed that students with delinquent behavior most of the time initiate harmful conflicts unhealthy relationships and render them unable to accept the opinion of others (Fortin, 2003).

In other words, juvenile delinquents lack the motivation to learn in school, causing them to give up on daily academic challenges and maintain a positive sense of self-worth. It was further claimed that school delinquents lack determination in attaining academic success. At the same time, those self-motivated students show optimistic personalities, high self-esteem, and have greater chances of excelling in school tasks (Lopes, Salovey, & Straus, 2003).

B. Anti-social Behavior of Juveniles

The general mean rating was 2.30 with a descriptive equivalent of low. The table shows that the juvenile seldom committed fighting on another person with mutual blows with a highest mean rating of 2.51 rather than attacking the police who tried to stop another person with the lowest score of 2.03.

The result of the study is consistent with the findings of the research concerning adolescent delinquency, where the level of delinquent behavior did not achieve 10%. 98.9% of the adolescents' delinquency is low, with only 1.1% adolescents at the high level. The study implied that the level of failure is controllable (Hassan, 2008).

Moreover, in the study on violence among adolescents, it was found that 10.7% of students had been involved in physical fights, 4.3 % committed theft, 2.7% for vandalism, and 2.4% for those who had a record of carrying a weapon. Although all these types of behavior can be manageable, with only a tiny percentage involved in delinquency, it is

still alarming. These could lead to more severe forms of crime and social problems (Lee et al., 2007).

Further, it was stated that there is no specific reason why some youngsters become aggressors; some factors are known to have influenced young people like family, peers, and the environment in general, which can develop bullying behavior in school. Those students who have aggressive behavior are more likely to become bullies, while those who are shy are more likely to become victims. A few studies suggest that many bullying problems may be caused by poor emotional management (Serrano, 2006).

It was also tested that emotional intelligence significantly impacts one's life, proving that it was a medium of development and satisfaction. Additionally, people who have a higher level of emotional intelligence are also more likely to opt to use adaptive mechanism traits against deviant and violent behavior and thus demonstrate a healthier psychological adjustment (Mayer et al., 2000).

Likewise, law enforcement officials attribute high truancy rates to daytime vandalism in other states, which means that students' high truancy rate has low academic achievements because truants are most likely to drop out of school (Heaviside et al., 1998).

Additionally, low parental monitoring, support, and constant family conflicts can contribute to adolescents' problem behaviors (Maneiro & Sobral, 2017). In this new generation, young people become more influenced by peer groups making more time associated with their peers of the same age. Difficulties related to the environment can increase the vulnerability of risky behaviors (Sehn et al., 2016).

C. Social Skills of Juveniles

As shown in the results, the overall mean rating for the level of social skills was 2.77, with the descriptive level of moderate. This implied that the juveniles sometimes experienced indicative statements.

Youngsters lacking social competence might become self-centered and unable to empathize and relate to others. Also, student delinquents often struggle with personal and emotional problems. Another factor that protects delinquent and violent behavior patterns is the psychological stability of a person, like the ability to be open to changes in school, good relationships, a sense of humor in dealing with negative situations, and the improvement of social skills (Erasmus, 2007).

In addition, social skills mean operating successfully in one's social environment. People with low social skills have difficulties interacting with others, limiting their opportunity to form and maintain good friendships with their peers, thereby limiting the number of their social relations. Social skills are a collection of learned behaviors giving the individual the ability to have a meaningful relationship with others and to abstain from socially unreasonable reactions. Cooperation, collaborating with others, helping, initiating a connection, requesting help, and praising and appreciating others are examples of this behavior. Learning the above

behaviors and creating influential relationships with others is most important in childhood. Unfortunately, some children do not understand these skills, so most children encounter adverse reactions from adults and other children (Agran et al., 2016).

Consequently, the process of socialization becomes crucial in adolescence. One of the most critical educational aims of childhood is developing social skills. The level of children's and adults' enjoyment of these skills influences their personal and social health and their academic success (Rawles, 2016).

Likewise, it is a transitional stage, during which young people experience physical, cognitive, and emotional changes and changes in social expectations and behavioral patterns (Jackson, 2020).

In recent times, state institutions have been increasingly focusing on developing social responsibility in the members of society. Social responsibility plays a vital role in enhancing cohesion within the community, organizing lives within it, and increasing interdependence and coherence among individuals. Social responsibility is also an expression of how closely an individual is associated with a community and their state and sense of belonging to family, society, and country. On the contrary, ignorance about our lack of social responsibility, or individuals' weak sense of social responsibility, represents a severe threat to society. Social responsibility is vital in making young people assume responsibilities; it prepares and allows them to perform their roles in the best possible way of building community. Also, a responsible individual of sound mental health and psychosocial well-being has a social responsibility toward oneself and others (Al-Kharashi, 2004).

D. Significance of the Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Social Skills of Juveniles

As revealed, all the indicators of emotional intelligence, when analyzed according to social skills, the obtained f-ratio between the specified ranges was .737 with a p-value of .000, which was lower than the 0.05 level of significance and which rejected the null hypothesis. In other words, there is a significant relationship between the level of emotional intelligence and the level of social skills of juveniles in the City of Mati.

The results showed that how juveniles deal with their emotions also affects how they interact with other people. Lack of emotional intelligence may lead to maladjustment and inability to achieve desired goals. Similarly, the relationship between low levels of emotional intelligence may influence the ability of a child to show and express their feelings to others. The ability to handle one's emotions is essential as this provides a framework to understand how emotional conflict affects social functioning. It may have a predictive value above and beyond cognitive intelligence about real-life outcomes.

Meanwhile, it was emphasized by Agran et al. (2016) adolescents need to learn appropriate social skills. In recent decades, in investigations of behavioral disorders and social

deviations, sociologists and psychologists have found that many diseases have their roots in individuals' inability to analyze themselves correctly and appropriately, the lack of control and personal adequacy counter difficult positions, and the lack of awareness to solve social difficulties and problems in an appropriate way (Zach et al., 2016).

Therefore, because of society's increasing changes and complexities, developing social communication and preparing individuals, especially young generations, seem essential to counter difficult positions. The development of humanity depends on individuals' scientific and cultural developments and advances, especially for youth, who are the human and intellectual reserves of our country, which is vital in influencing their development. More research and discourse on the factors affecting this advance, especially social intellect and skills and their components, are required in this connection.

E. Significance of the Relationship Between Antisocial Behavior and Social Skills of Juveniles

The result showed the overall rating of the f-ratio, which was .073 with a p-value of .209, which was greater than the 0.05 level of significance and which failed to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between anti-social behavior and social skills of juveniles in the City of Mati.

The result of this study was corroborated with the findings that the pathways to delinquency start at the onset of early child life. These behavioral problems often are followed by progressively more severe behavioral and adjustment problems in adulthood, including aggression. Further, adults who were frequently truant as teenagers are much more likely to have poorer health and mental problems, lower-paying jobs, an increased chance of living in poverty, more reliance on welfare support, children who exhibit problem behaviors, and an increased likelihood of incarceration (Kelley et al., 1997).

Children who have not acquired appropriate social skills develop psychological problems such as unsuccessful communication with peers, inappropriate educational performance, not participating in activities and isolation, rejection by peers, anxiety, depression, and anger in childhood and throughout life (Anastasi, 1990).

F. Significance on the Influence of Emotional Intelligence and Anti-social Behavior on the Social Skills of Juveniles

The result of the study revealed that emotional intelligence shows a strong significant influence on the social skills of juveniles. In contrast, anti-social behavior shows no effect on juveniles' level of social skills. This further concluded that the null hypothesis for the influence of emotional intelligence and social skills was rejected while the impact of anti-social behavior and social skills were accepted. This also implied that emotional intelligence affects an individual's social skills while anti-social behavior does not influence social skills.

More so, juvenile delinquency shows the path of maladaptive behaviors, conduct disorder, and other

behavioral problems, which are often followed by more serious behavioral issues in the course of adulthood, which could also lead to violent behavior and maladjustments, like in an instance, bullies display a shallow level of emotional intelligence which means their social skills and self-control are also affected (Zimmerman, 2005).

Moreover, in this study, anti-social behavior means the delinquent acts committed by juveniles, such as school crime, vandalism, aggression, anti-normative conduct, theft, and illegal drug use. The early onset of delinquency significantly increases the risk of committing heinous crimes and signs of violent behaviors in later years. Similarly, in the context of this study, these inappropriate behaviors usually happen in school. They are also believed to be the rooting causes of academic failure, deterioration of the mind, impairment of socioemotional status, juvenile delinquency, and crimes (Moffitt, 1993).

With the given results tabulated in the preceding chapter, this research reaffirms the proposition of Goleman (1995) that emotional intelligence and social skills are all interconnected processes and abilities. Pool researchers suggest that there is perhaps a hierarchy and higher levels such as self-regulation and self-motivation, which requires a much greater level of emotional intelligence than the lowest level known as perception.

The result also supports the model, which claimed that a student who possesses a higher score in emotional intelligence had been attributed to a person more skilled in perceiving and understanding other people's emotions and possesses better social skills. This also supports the development of more appropriate behavior patterns with their peers (Mayer and Salovey, 1997).

However, there is minimal evidence of studies and literature that have analyzed the relationship between emotional intelligence and social skills and anti-social behavior committed by adolescents. Thus, the researcher's current research aims to describe the relationship between these three variables.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the study's finding, the overall level of emotional intelligence is moderate, which means that the juveniles sometimes manifest it. Its indicators revealed good results for self-awareness, self-motivation, and self-regulation. Moreover, the overall level of anti-social behavior is low, which justifies that the juveniles seldom committed anti-social behavior.

In the aspect of social skills, the researcher concluded that there is a moderate level of social skills among the juveniles as represented by interpersonal behavior, self-related behavior, task-related behavior, and environment-related behavior. The researcher further concludes that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and social skills of juveniles since the p-value obtained a 0.000 lesser than 0.05. Moreover, there is no meaningful relationship between the variables anti-social behavior and children's social skills since the result revealed in the

previous chapter the p-value of .209, which is higher than 0.05.

Remarkably, emotional intelligence has significantly affected the social skills of juveniles. However, in the domains of anti-social behavior, only theft, vandalism, and drug-related indicators best influenced the indicator task-related behavior of the social skills of the juveniles. The rest of the domains, such as aggression and anti-normative conduct, cannot control social skills without the assistance of the other factors.

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